

WOMEN OFFERED TO THE TEMPLES OF NAGAPATTINAM REGION

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Abstract:

This research explicits the reason for the name Nagapattinam districts. It speaks on the villages of Nagapattinam districts and under which village it located in the interim period. And also this research paper explains with companions to the offerings has been offered by other lineage women and also the queens of Cholas when worked sincerely to god.

Introduction:

In the later period of Cholas, the rock inscription helps us to know the deeds were given by the women of the king's family. There are nineteen rock inscriptions help us to know the deeds given by the women. They are respectively, Uttamachola (A.D 970-985), Kulottunga-I (A.D 1070-1120), Vikramachola (A.D 1118-1135), Rajaraja II (1146-1163), Rajadhiraja II (A.D 1163-1178), Kulottunga III (A.D 1178-1218), and Rajakesari rock inscriptions and are unknown named rock inscriptions. These rock inscriptions would be known from the temple of Nagapattinam regions. Athur, Aavarani, Keezhvalur, Korukkai, Sembian Madevi, Tiruvaimoor, and Thiruvelvikudi.

Athur village is located in the Mayiladuthurai region, Nagapattinam district. It is about 20 kilo-meter north-west from Mayiladuthurai. In the period of Cholas, it was a part in Virutarajapayangaravalanaattu Kurukkai. The names of the temple and the gods could be called as Thiruvudai Tittaiudaiyar temple¹. This is mentioned in the temple rock-inscriptions as Virutarajapayangaravalanaattu Kurukkainaattu brahmadeyam Sri Rajanarayana chaturvedimangalathu udaiyarthiruvudai Tittaiudaiyar. An important temple in that region is the village 'korukkai'. It is about 12 kilo-meters north-west from Mayiladuthurai. It was a part in the Virutarajapayangaravalanaattu Vikramacholachaturvedimangalam, in the sixth ruling year of Rajathiraja II².

Tiruvelvikudi, about 14 kilometers west from Mayiladuthurai was a part of Kurukkainaattu brahmadeyam videl vidugudevi chaturvedimangalam, in the twelfth ruling year of Uttamachola³. This village was 'Keeyamanickavalanaattu brahmadeyam' in the tenth reign of the Rajaraja-II⁴. It is called as 'Keyamanickavalanaattu thenkalchakarapatru aabaranathan'. It is seen in the rock-inscription of Ananda Narayana Perumal⁵.

In the regional of Nagapattinam, Sembianmadevi is a special place. Sembianmadevi is a wife of Gandaradityan and the mother of Uttamacholan. So that the village would be called as Sembianmadevi chaturvedimangalam. The rock-inscription of Uttamachola's fifteenth regnal year called as 'Thenkarai Alanaattu Brahmadeyam Sembian Madevi chaturvedimangalam'⁶. In the twelfth regional year of Vikramachola, Tiruvaimur would be called as 'Rajendracholavalanaattu vendazhaivelurkootrathu thiruvaimur'⁷. By means of these rock-inscription we could know the historical values of the villages and its women and their deeds given.

Reason for the Name Nagapattinam:

Nagapattinam was a great place in the ancient times. This district was very famous for Literature, inscription, archaeology and other departments. This place would

be sung by Gnanasambandar as 'Kalangalvootham Kazhisul Kadalnagai Kaaronam' and 'Kadaikkolselvam Kazhisool Kadalnagai'. And Thirunavukarasar sung this as 'Kalangalserkadalnagaikaaronam'⁸. Ptolemy called this place as 'Nigama'⁹. Religions like Buddhism, Jainism, Saivism, Vaisnavism, were in that place in a great women. The rock-inscription of regional temple expresses the deeds given by women.

Women Presented Silver Kalasas:

In the 16th regnal year (A.D 976) of Parantakan Madevadigal, mother of Uttamachola, Sembian Madeviyar donated 142 kalanju (1 kalanju=1.77 kilo-grams) of Silvert to Manavalesvarar temple, Thiruvetikudi¹⁰. It is given in the rock-inscription as, "Sembianmadevikuduthavellikalasamondruithunirainootrunarpathuirukalanju".

Women Donated Food to the Brahmins:

In the 12th regnal year of Uttamachola (A.D 982), the wives of Uttamachola, Pattana Dhanathongiyar, Mazhapadithennavan Madeviyar, Irungolar daughter Vanavan Madeviyar, Vizhuparaiyar Mahalar, daughter of Pazhuvettariyar donated 905 kalanju (1 kalanju=1.77 grams of gold) to Sri Kailasamudaiyar temple in the birth date of their mother-in-law, Sembian Madeviyar¹¹. The temple trustees donated fed the Brahmins by means the golden deeds given.

Land Donated by Women:

In the 15th regnal year of Uttamachola (A.D.984), Thirubhuvana Madeviyar received sales land from various people and both to the gods every month, and burning of temple lamps, and fed to the Brahmins, it is given the rock-inscription of Sri Kailasamudaiya Mahadevar temple built by Sembian Madevi. It is clearly known by the areas of the lands. The Sembian Madevi Channel, Kandaradityan Channel, Pazhuvur Nakkam Channel, Paratakan Madevi Channel and Madevadigal Channel. And Uttamacholavathi (Veethi or Street), Kandaradityavathi, Tirailokiya Sundaravathi, Sembian Madevivathi, Madevadigal Vathi and Sembianmadevicherri were the borders¹².

Golden Things Donated by Women:

In the regnal year of Uttamachola, his wife Bhattandhanathongiyar donated a golden Kite to Sri Kailayamudaiyar temple¹³. Panjavan Madeviyar, an another wife donated 53.1 grams of gold weight stick (Vensamarai)¹⁴. Sonna Madeviyar alias Kannapparasi donated 507.5 kalanju (898.275 grams of gold) to the Sri Kailamudaiyar temple trustees¹⁵. The rock-inscription expresses "Kannappayarasiyarana sonna mahadeviyar ivvurur kallal kuduthom pon ainootru ezhukalanjarai".

The wife of the king, Aaruran Ambalathadigal donated 143 kalanju (253.11 grams of gold) Urattaiyar Sorappayar, an another wife donated 145 kalanju (256.65 grams of gold) to Sri Kailasamudaiyar temple¹⁶. After receiving those golden things to the temple trustees spent for temple and donated to the people in the day of Sembian Madeviyar's birth, in the month of Sitthirai, kettai day.

Women Donated Deeds with Records:

In the 10th regnal year of Kulottunga I (A.D 1080), Vellatti Ariyal (shepherd's woman), Sembian Kandiyur, donated deeds to Thiruvetikudi Manavalesvarar temple to perpetual lamps. She gave this to the four Brahmins to the temple. For which she gave a documents also. It was a part in *Virutharaja payangaravalanaattu Kurukkainaattu Gagaikondasola chaturvedimangalam, Thiruvetikudi* in the period of Kulottunga chola I¹⁷.

Palace Women Donated Paddy:

In the 13th regnal year of Rajaraja II (A.D 1158), Agamudaiyal narayani, wife of Matthiyasthan Virutharajapayangaravalanadu, donated deeds¹⁸. This king's

Veeratanesvarar temple rock-inscription expresses the deeds given by a women. That woman was Arayan Umaiyazhvi. She donated to the Thirusamundesvaramudaiyar, Panaiyur Thirupalliyarai nacchiar and Nayaga Devar, for which Siva Brahmins received one hundred and twenty paisa. From the interest received from the money they helped to donated as Kurunilrunaazhi (6 padi) per day¹⁹.

Women Donated Lands for Dwelling:

In the 18th regnal year of Rajaraja II (A.D1163), the wife of kuravacherri Semoolathanabhattachan and Audaiyarchani, wife of Perupatrapuliyur Vinayagabhattachan donated lands to Kediliyappar temple, Keezhvelurat Nagapattinam. They donated fertile lands for garden and donated land for the people who maintain the garden. This land was in Saathangudi in the name of Sentaamaraikannan Kollai²⁰.

Family Member's Donation:

In the 21st regnal year of Rajaraja II (A.D1167), the families from Athur donated lands to Aathisandesvara Devakanmigal, Swarnapuresvarartemple, Athur. Dhakshinamoorthibhattachan, father of Rajarajacherri Abhisithar and his brother and Matha Periyandal sold the lands. They sold the land, Jayasimhakulakalanallur for rupees 12,600²¹.

Women Donated Coins:

Kaalingarayan's wife Arayan Saamundi, daughter of Kurukularayar, Panaiyurnattu Aanangur Udaiyar sold their lands for rupees one thousand. It is seen in the Swarnapuresvarar temple rock-inscription of Kulottungachola's at Athur²².

Women Donated Lamps to the Temple:

In the 26th regnal year of Kulottungachola III (A.D1194), wife of the merchant Thirunageswaramudaiyan, udaiyanacchisivan Perundevi donated 600 coins to Thiruvaimur temple. The member of the Brahmins were collected coins from her. For the burning lamps to the temple, they used the interest amount from the coins, they donated and they paved a way to donated ghee for three Sevidu (1 sevidu=360 paddy) and also she donated a brass oil-lamp²³. The rock-inscription expresses as, "*Sivanperundevi Vubaiya mangai vaitha Santhivilakku moontru nayanar thirumunbu erikkaivalitta Pithalai kuthuvilakku iruppu*". Poonangai donated a lamp to Thiyagarajar temple, Thiruvaimur and she gave 112 coins to Sivabrahmanas to burn a lamp to the Thiruvaimur temple²⁴.

Donation of a Servant Maid:

In the 16th regnal year of Rajakesarippanman, Thiruvadi Rayarialias Umabhattacharagiworked in the palace sold the land for 16 kalanju (28.32 grams of gold). She donated the lands to Manavalesvarar temple, Thiruvelvikudi. It is seen in the temple rock-inscription²⁵.

Women Donated Granite:

Karaimalla Nanangai, wife of Veerantarayana Pallavarayar donated six granite stone donated for the holy work of the Manavalesvarar temple, Thiruvelvikudi. It is seen in the rock-inscription lines, "*Veeranaraya Pallavarayarpratti Karaimalla naanangai ita kal aaru*"²⁶.

Women Donated Land:

In the 10th regnal year of Sadayavarman Kulasekhara Pandya (A.D1247), Thiruvidainacchiar, Ellaarkunacchiar donated 6.67 acres (1 veli) of lands to Ponmalaikundrudaiyar Sivan temple²⁷. This message is seen in the rock-inscription of the temple AananthaNarayanaperumal temple, Aarani in Nagappattinam. It is seen in the rock-inscription lines, "*Nilam velium innayanarku iraiyiliyaga uthagabrahamanam Eluthi kodutthom, Thiruvidainacchiarum, Ellarkunacchiarum intha nilam velium*"²⁸.

Conclusion:

In the mid-period, women were the owners of the land. Kings lineage women donated lands to the regional temple of Nagapattinam. It is seen in the rock-inscription. It also expresses the deeds and donation of other lineage women. Their character also seen. For example Sembiyan Madevi occupied an eminent place by character among those women in the period. For example we may quote the temple built by her, Sri Kailasamudaiyar Mahadevar, Thirukodika, Thiruthurithi, Thirumananjeri, Thiruvakkarai, Thenkurangaduthurai, Aanankur. She donated land and many things to the temple for burning lamps, foods and other things.

Daughter-in-laws of Sembiyan Mahadevi, Kannapparasi, Sonnamadevi, Aaruran Ambalathadigalar, Thirubhuvanamideviyar, Thanathongiyar, Malapadidevan Madeviyar, Irunkolar Mahalar Vanavan Mahadeviyar, Vizhuparaiyar Mahalar, Pazhuvettaraiyan Mahalar donated lands and gold to the temple built by their mother-in-law Sembiyanmadeviyar. In the mid-period, Sivan Perundevi, Devaratiyar Poonangai donated coins. In addition to that, Arayan Samundi, wife of Kalingarayar donated lands to the temple it gave more reputation. It could be seen that the recent women also donated coins. For example, in recent days women dedicated the temple with the help of men in the festival days. Sometimes they donated paddy, foods and gold to the goddess and adorning the goddess by silk sarees and donated cattles. Then they donated those things for the fruitfulness of their family life. These deeds will be continued in future also.

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